

DIVINFOOD

**Co-constructing interactive short and mid-tier food chains
to value agrobiodiversity in healthy plant-based food**

Deliverable 7.5

Mid-term review of Living Labs functioning

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Executive summary

Objectives

Living Labs (LLs) play a key role within DIVINFOOD: for this reason, Work Package 7 on “Coordination and management”, the project’s Grant Agreement envisaged a Task (7.2) specifically aimed at monitoring LL activities. The aim of this deliverable is thus to lay out the LL’s achievements both in terms of the tangible and intangible outputs produced so far (i.e. the **what**) and the process followed to reach that point (i.e. the **how**), as the two are inextricably linked.

Approach

In addition to the tangible and intangible outputs expected from LLs, the project documents gave precise indications as to how LLs were to be organised in order to best achieve the project’s goals.

First of all, the LLs are expected to include a diversity of actors along the value chain and cover different roles. Secondly, given that co-learning and co-creation are key approaches of the project, emphasis is placed on the use of **participatory** approaches. A third feature of the project refers to how to engage stakeholders and above all how to maintain an **engagement** high during the length of the project, while the last aspect relates to the way LLs grow or **recruit** new members. This last feature is important because one of the aims of the project is to establish the 9 LLs as laboratories and demonstration sites of how to set up territorial networks that value agrobiodiversity.

Based on the above, the key questions in monitoring LLs in the past two years have been:

1. Achievements: **What** have the LLs achieved or co-produced, in the last two years?
2. Process: **How** have they done this? Did they involve a diversity of stakeholders and who are they? How were stakeholders engaged and participation stimulated? How are new stakeholders recruited?

To answer these questions, the deliverable uses a mix of primary and secondary data. Among the former, we have set an online monitoring tool and carried out informal conversations with LL Coordinators online or physically at Annual Meetings and other gatherings. Secondary data includes the results of the Mid-Term Review and outputs produced by previous Milestones and other events.

Teams involved

University of Pisa (Dalia Mattioni and Francesca Galli), INRAE (Yuna Chiffolleau), all LL Coordinators, Open Food France (Samuel Feller), INRAE Transfert (Vincent Troillard).

1. Introduction

Living Labs (LLs) have been extensively used since the 1990s in the context of the EU’s funding of a variety of research and innovation projects. LLs have been used for a range of disciplines or sectors – initially related mostly to computer science, information and communication technology as well as innovation management and business, and later also for projects focusing on the agri-food system (Leminen and Westerlund, 2012; Gamache et al, 2020). The creation of the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) by the European Commission in 2006 shows how important this tool is for EU-funded projects that aim to foster innovation through a co-creation process that involves a wide range of stakeholders. Many authors have defined LLs (e.g. Folstad, 2008; Leminen and Westerlund, 2012) and their definitions resemble that developed by the ENoLL in 2015 that defines LLs as: “user-centred, open innovation ecosystems based on a systematic user co-creation approach, integrating research and innovation processes in real life communities and settings”, where users can be intended as the citizens or end customers who participate in the LL, but also those who benefit from the result of the work.

Living Labs play a key role also within DIVINFOOD (see next section), and it is because of their key role that under Work Package 7 on “Coordination and management”, the project’s Grant Agreement envisaged a Task (7.2) specifically aimed at monitoring LL activities. The Mid Term Review (MTR) Report team also highlighted the importance of LL participation, and particularly the need to keep engagement high over the life of the project. The aim of this deliverable is thus to lay out the LL’s achievements both in terms of the tangible and intangible outputs produced so far (i.e. the what) and the process followed to reach that point (i.e. the how), as the two are inextricably linked.

The Deliverable is organised in the following way. Section 2 outlines the role of Living Labs within the DIVINFOOD project and its Work Packages, and what was and is expected of them. In light of this it identifies a series of key questions to guide the monitoring exercise. Section 3 describes the methodology used to answer such questions including sources and data analysis. Section 4 illustrates the results first across Living Labs to provide an overview, and then by Living Labs to provide further details, particularly on the “how”. Section 5 concludes by identifying broad themes emerging around the key monitoring questions.

2. The Living Labs in DIVINFOOD and what is expected of them

As mentioned above, LLs play a key role within DIVINFOOD. The project has set up 9 LLs, some of which were already active before joining the project (advanced) while others were created in the frame of DIVINFOOD (emerging). Each LL focuses on crops that are underused in their countries (in breeding, in the field and for food). Below is a table (Table 1) that summarises key information of each LL, namely: name, location, NUC used and objectives. The table draws on a table previously

created for Deliverable 5.1 on “Framework for Living Lab facilitation and data production”¹ and enriches it with information drawn from the workplans developed by each Living Lab under Milestone 3 “Living Labs’ configurations and programmes validated by Partners of the project” (October 2022).

<i>Name, location of LL and stage of development</i>	<i>NUCs and motto</i>	<i>Objectives to be achieved in 5 years</i>
Bean-Lyon – Lyon surroundings, Eastern France (emerging)	“Meat bean” “Meat bean revival process is “on” but climate change does not help!	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increase meat bean cultivation and consumption 2. Show that a NUC can develop a viable economic, social and environmental local ecosystem 3. Based on the success of the meat bean, local actors will reproduce it with other NUCs
Bean-Cast – Castelnaudary area, South-west of France (emerging)	Lingot bean Make a traditional local dish that drives the agro-ecological transition of the territory	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Develop a local organic production of lingot bean 2. NUCs used in the school canteens 3. New cassoulet’s recipes available at local events
Cer-Occ – South western regions of France (advanced)	Einkorn, rivet wheat Collective dynamics in Occitanie to discover minor cereals and increase their use	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Einkorn and rivet wheat cultivars disseminated with relevant knowledge material 2. NUCs used in the school canteens 3. Export and share the “einkorn network”
Leg-ItSwitz Switzerland, Italy (emerging)	White lupin Lupinus (and Pisum) in fabula: making legume-based foods a fairy tale for farmers up to consumers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lupin firmly established as an ingredient in food recipes 2. Demonstration of multiple benefits of lupins at agroecological, nutritional and economic levels 3. Solid basis for follow-up/upscale
GPea-Port Portugal (emerging)	Grass pea A white grass pea here, a blue grass pea there, an attractive grass pea for everybody everywhere	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A bigger number of happy grass pea farmers 2. A diversity of attractive grass pea varieties and production systems in the field 3. Healthy and tasty innovative food products based on grass pea on the market

¹ Massari, S., Mattioni, D., Galli, F. (2022) *Framework for LL facilitation and Data Production*. Deliverable 5.1. DIVINFOOD H2020 project, September, 2022 [available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/8382431>]

Leg-Hung Hungary (advanced)	Local landraces of chickpea, cowpea and common bean To (re)introduce (Hungary) less-known and/or traditional legume species into Hungarian gastronomy- from School catering to premium kitchens	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Availability of seeds and handbooks on small- scale cultivations 2. Larger farmers involved in production to increase volume 3. Restaurants develop recipes and start selling the dishes based on the NUCs
Cer-Hung Hungary (emerging)	Einkorn Healthy and locally produced food for everyone. (Re)introduce ancient cereal species into Hungarian gastronomy via traditional and innovative products	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. More cultivars available for farmers 2. Guidelines of pre-processing and agricultural practices 3. Improved consumer consciousness – aware of the value of ancient cereals
Faba-Nord Denmark and Sweden (emerging)	Faba bean Developing a successful value chain on Nordic faba beans – easily grown and tasty	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Plant-based food based on Nordic grown faba beans 2. Farmers growing well-adapted varieties for quality food 3. Consumer awareness of faba beans as nutritious, tasty and healthy food
Leg-Nord Denmark and Sweden (emerging)	Blue lupine, grey pea, lentils Well-adapted grain legumes from the North	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Local production of well-adapted varieties of high value 2. Established value chains for Nordic grain legumes for food 3. Farmers know how to grow grain legumes with success

Table 1. A brief description of the 9 DIVINFOOD LLs

The projects’ overall goal is to “facilitate the use and increase the value of Neglected and Underutilised Crops (NUCs) in food chains” (Grant Agreement, Part B), and in order to reach this goal it is organised in eight Work Packages (WPs), five of which (WP 1-5) contain the core of the project activities. LLs play a central role in reaching DIVINFOOD’s objectives and are the “place” where these activities occur. Almost all of DIVINFOOD’s WP tasks occur within LLs, be they assessment of varietal performance, focus groups with consumers on expectations regarding NUC-based food chains, experimentation with innovative pre-processing technique and other activities. Table 2 below summarises what is expected by LLs under each WP for the 5 years of the project. In other words, it summarises WHAT LLs are expected to produce by the end of the 5 years of the project.

<i>Work Package</i>	<i>Description</i>
WP 1: Diversify consumer-producer interactions to guide innovation in short and mid-tier chains and facilitate responsible consumption	LLs' work will focus on working on the end users of the value chains, i.e. consumers first considered as citizens. Their work will focus on understanding consumer expectations and experience around agrobiodiversity and NUCs to better co-design products, transformation and marketing processes that will be valued and appreciated by consumers. They will also work with consumers to develop tools that better transmit the value of NUCs from producers to consumers, such as digital tools, and interactive and transparent marketing channels to increase and stabilise the sales of NUCs.
WP 2: Co-produce new and diversified healthy plant-based products and recipes	LLs' work will concentrate on co-producing food products and recipes from minor cereals and grain legumes. The LLs will evaluate the quality and safety of the raw material produced under WP3 and WP4, they will renew traditional dishes where relevant, and will optimise innovative mild processing techniques specifically suited to short and mid-tier chains. They will work closely with key actors, such as farmers-processors, small-scale food companies and chefs to enhance their capacity to innovate with the new products, always in interaction with consumers.
WP 3: Co-develop ecosystem services-based agroecological farming systems	The bulk of LLs' work will be to identify and/or co-develop agroecological farming systems that improve NUC's performance and their delivery of ecosystem services. LLs will work to assess and benchmark the performance of various GxE combinations, where G are the NUC genotypes and E are the different types of ecological and socio-economical environments. The LLs will focus on a participatory assessment of the services that the combinations create and will facilitate and improve NUC crops pre-processing.
WP 4: Co-breed under-utilised biodiversity for markets	The focus of the LLs will be to co-develop improved varieties of NUCs. This will involve the participatory identification of available genetic resources, the development of locally adapted/improved varieties of NUCs and the multiplication of seeds. This will also include a foresight exercise on "future seeds" in each LL.
WP 5: Co-construct business models and territorial networks to support biodiversity use in value-based chains and make policy recommendations	In this WP, LLs will focus on three levels. At the farm/food business level, LLs will be involved in data collection on benefits and costs related to cultivating and processing NUCs, to identify the (more or less successful) business models. At the territorial level, LLs will identify the organisational and institutional mechanisms for effective valorisation of NUCs. Lastly, on a broader level, LLs will provide input for policy analysis and recommendations.

Table 2. Summary of LLs' role within each of DIVINFOOD's core WPs

In addition to the tangible and intangible outputs expected from LLs, the DoA gave precise indications as to HOW LLs were to be organised in order to best reach the project’s goals. First of all, and in line with the literature that describes how LLs function (Hossain et al., 2019), the LLs are expected to “enact a **multi-actor** approach” by including “various types of stakeholders involved in value chains: farmers, small-scale processors, chefs, food hubs developers, consumers, and local authorities” (part B – page 6). This is closely tied with the objectives of the project that aim to develop the full value of NUCs from seed to plate, and thus be spaces where a diversity of actors from across the chain can come together and work alongside researchers to creatively co-produce innovative ways of managing and valuing agrobiodiversity.

Co-learning and co-creation are indeed key approaches of the project, where the former includes activities such as joint data collection and participatory assessments while co-creation refers to the tangible outputs of the project, such as field experiments, trials and recipes for example. The key term here is “co”, i.e. a joint and collaborative effort. For this reason, a second key feature of the HOW LLs are organised is the emphasis on the use of **participatory** approaches. In this respect, ample guidance was given by Deliverable 5.1 (“Framework for LL facilitation and data production”) as to the types of tools to be used to best stimulate participation ranging from more traditional face-to-face chaired meetings to the use of online interactive tools and social media. A key feature of the deliverable refers to how to engage stakeholders and above all how to maintain that **engagement** high during the length of the project. This last point was stressed during the review of the first reporting period in 2023.

A third feature related to the way LLs are organized and work relates to how LLs grow or **recruit** new members. This feature is important because one of the aims of the project, as outlined in the DoA is that of “stabilizing LLs into territorial multi-actor networks over the course of the project” (part B – page 8). The DIVINFOOD project therefore uses the 9 LLs as laboratories and demonstration sites of how to proceed in setting up territorial networks that value agrobiodiversity.

Based on the above, the key questions in monitoring LLs in the past two years have been:

1. Achievements: **What** have the LLs achieved or co-produced in the last two years?
2. Process: **How** have they done this? Did they involve a diversity of stakeholders and who are they? How were stakeholders engaged and participation stimulated? How are new stakeholders recruited?

3. Methodology

To answer the above two questions the Deliverable used a diverse set of sources. *Primary data* was collected by using two tools:

- An online form that was filled by LL Coordinators every time the LL met or whenever it organised events/workshops or key activities with partners. Data was collected up until 31/5/2024. Key data collected was: objective/s of the meeting, type of audience, audience size, whether the objective/s of the meeting were met, whether there were any people who came for the first time, whether there were stakeholders who did not show up, and

what tools were used to facilitate the meetings. See Appendix 1 for a complete list of the questions.

- Informal conversations with LL Coordinators online or physically at Annual Meetings and other gatherings (Ex-Com meetings, personal communications, LL meetings, etc). Notes were taken during these conversations. Notes were also taken during stakeholder days in Annual Meetings and during inter-LL workshops.

Initially, the DoA plans the organisation of exchanges between LLs coordinators once per month by videoconference to present the progress, expose problems, find solutions, and better identify subjects for cross-comparisons in WPs. The UniPi and INRAE partners felt that this approach was not only too cumbersome, but also unsuitable: the rhythm of an LL is not regular, alternating between periods of intense activity and periods of lower activity. In addition, finding common dates for all the LL coordinators once a month was not a realistic objective. We therefore adapted the monitoring protocol with an online tool and informal interviews every six months, while the annual meetings made it possible to develop comparisons between LLs, including in terms of how they operate.

Secondary sources included the Mid Term Review (MTR) Report that covered project activities from the 1st March 2022 to the 31st August 2023, the workplan produced by each LL under Milestone 3 (see Appendix 2 for the template of the workplan), the two posters produced for the two Annual Meetings of 2023 and 2024 (see Appendix 3 for a template of the posters).

Data was analysed against *what* the LLs co-produced together (tangible outputs) and *how* they went about their activities as laid out in the DoA. The data and the analysis are laid out in the following way. With an aim of giving the reader who may not be well-versed with the work of the LLs an overview of WHAT the LLs have achieved per WP, **Section 4.1** provides such an **overview**. The data on what the LLs collectively produced is drawn from the MTR report and is complemented by data drawn from the online tool and the informal conversations (See Table 3).

Section 4.2 expands on the previous section and summarises not only WHAT the LLs have achieved (and provides more detail) but adds information as to HOW they have achieved it. This information is given **for each LL**. Each LL section is made up of two sub-sections:

1. Achievements: WHAT did the LL do in the first 2 years of the project? This uses data emerging from the Mid Term Review of the project complemented by the data emerging from the online tool and the informal conversations.
2. Process: How the LLs did it. This is further subdivided into sub-headings:
 - *Who was involved in the multi-stakeholder LL?* Here a table describes the LL stakeholders (first column) in 3 different moments of the project (subsequent columns). The source for the information for October 2022 is the information contained in MS3 (Validation of LL plans) while the information for the last two columns comes from the posters prepared for the Annual Meetings (Portugal and Denmark-Sweden respectively). The data is presented in a cumulative way, i.e. columns 2 and 3 show the NEW stakeholders only. DIVINFOOD partners are indicated in bold.
 - *How are stakeholders engaged and participation stimulated?*
 - *How are new stakeholders recruited?*

The data elaborated under these last two headings comes from the online tool and the informal conversations with LL Coordinators.

The concluding Section 5 focuses on the process data, identifying a series of broad themes emerging from the three main questions illustrated above.

4. Results - What the Living Labs produced and how they did it

4.1 Across Living Labs

This section describes what the LLs have achieved in terms of outputs WP per WP, with a view to giving the reader an overview of what the LLs have done in the past two years. The information is provided in table form to make its consultation easier. In line with the MTR conclusions, all activities that were envisaged to be taking place in the first 18 months, were indeed carried out. The table below provides more information on the subsequent 9 months thanks to the online monitoring tool.

Tasks and expected activities (per WP)	What did the LL do in the first 24 months?
WP 1 - Diversify consumer-producer interactions to guide innovation in short and mid-tier chains and facilitate responsible consumption	
Task 1.1: online surveys and focus groups in LLs on consumers' knowledge, expectations and aversions	LLs organised the focus groups, dedicated to collect citizen-consumers' expectations and aversions regarding the use of agrobiodiversity in food chains, from breeding to marketing.
Task 1.2: Analysing NUC-based products values in food environments	Limited LL involvement - mostly secondary data collected.
Task 1.3: Workshops with consumers to rank Biodiversity Use indicators – input from all LLs. Creation of a Valuation Toolbox.	Has not occurred yet.
Task 1.4: Prototype mobile interactive app developed for each LL region	Has not occurred yet.

WP 2 - Co-produce new and diversified healthy plant-based products and recipes	
Task 2.1: Co-creation of innovative/renew and diversified plant based healthy and tasty food products and recipes	Legumes and minor cereals species or varieties have been incorporated in a diversity of innovative/renewed recipes and products. For example, two types of innovative fermented products with legumes started to be developed in two LLs (dairy like products with lupin, miso from grass pea). In addition, the development of mixed NUC legume-cereal or just minor cereal innovative foods were initiated in 3 LLs, for biscuits, bread, pasta or bulgur. Finally, NUC legume based innovative recipes have been developed in 3 LLs, by LLs' stakeholders, among whom famous chefs.
Task 2.2: Food and raw material quality evaluations	LLs have begun the quality analysis of food and raw NUC material. This means that some NUCs, whether raw or as mild processed food material (flour and pasta), have started to be characterised along a diversity of nutritional/health, organoleptic/sensorial and technological quality parameters, giving new data to contribute to the increase of their market value.
Task 2.3: Evaluation tools for quality traits valuable by consumers (in two LLs: Leg-ItSwitz and GPea-Port)	As planned, easy to apply, low cost quality evaluation tools of NUCs raw materials, based on spectrophotometry and spectroscopy, started to be developed for anti-nutritional and health beneficial compounds in white lupin seed and grass pea flour in LLs Leg-ITSwitz and Gpea-Port respectively. Even though this is a research laboratory activity, the researchers have taken into account criteria that are important to the LL's stakeholders, and which were highlighted at the LL meetings.
Task 2.4: Setting up of a Community of Practice around mild processing of legumes and cereals	All LLs have been meeting/engaging stakeholders to share knowledge and innovation on legume and cereals processing approaches with newcomers to allow a more direct interaction among stakeholders in national languages on different processing approaches. Some cross-LLs events have also taken place to the same end. A webinar series, to which all LLs were invited, was launched with a first edition on legumes and cereals fermentation.
WP 3 - Co-develop ecosystem services-based agroecological farming systems	
Task 3.1: Compiling experiences and data on NUCs performances	Farmers and other relevant stakeholders from each LL were interviewed as key informants to provide data for the Report. Thanks to this information Deliverable 3.1 on "Repertoire of local farms and farming systems using NUC.s in agroecology" was delivered in March 2024.
Task 3.2: Testing and assessing agrobiodiversity under diverse agroecological farming systems	In preparation for this task, and as part of the WP4, the LLs organised a workshop to carry out a participatory selection of NUC genotypes that were introduced into their on-farm and experimental sites trials. Trials of the selected NUCs were then implemented in the

	nine LLs, mainly on-farm and, in some LLs, in research stations, agricultural high schools' training fields and citizens' gardens, under diverse agroecological farming systems. They are still ongoing and initial assessment data is being collected.
Task 3.3: Participatory assessment of ecosystem services of agrobiodiversity in use	A list of tools and guidelines were made available to all LLs for the participatory assessment of the ecosystem services provided by their NUCs. Based on these, all LLs carried out workshop to jointly decide which ecosystem services would be assessed out of a list of pre-selected ecosystem services and their indicators.
Task 3.4: On-farm storage and pre-processing	The LLs contributed in the collection of data on on-farm storage and pre-processing (current practices, innovations and difficulties) with an aim to provide the data for Deliverable 3.6 "Repertoire of technical and organisational solutions for pre-processing stages". In collecting the data, important aspects of NUC harvesting and sorting were discussed with the farmers involved in the LL.
WP 4 - Co-breed under-utilised biodiversity for markets	
Task 4.1: Developing an interactive catalogue of underutilised cereals and legumes	Involvement of LL stakeholders in France, Portugal and Italy to co-design the interactive catalogue.
Task 4.2: Participatory breeding	The multi-actor breeding of varieties for local adaptation and product quality was completed by all LLs and a second year of breeding trials is underway.
Task 4.3: Lab breeding white lupine and pea	Two LLs (Leg-ItSwitz and GPea-Port) advanced on the development of molecular breeding tools for white lupin and for grass-pea. Even though this is a research laboratory activity, the researchers have taken into account criteria that are important to the LL's stakeholders, and which were highlighted at the LL meetings.
Task 4.4: 6 workshops on priorities for future plant breeding	Has not occurred yet.
WP 5 - Co-construct business models and territorial networks to support biodiversity use in value-based chains and make policy recommendations	
Task 5.1: Conceptual framework and methodology for LLs activities and data collection	All LLs produced a work plan for the rest of the project's life (MS3)
Task 5.2: New business models for farmers and small-scale processors	All LLs are responsible for providing information and/or contacts that will serve to fill in the GxE database which, in turn, will help to identify new business models.

Task 5.3: Territorial networks and governance arrangements	Eight study cases of inspiring initiatives in matter of NUCs territorial governance and economic support have been done based on information provided by some LLs.
Task 5.4: Produce a policy brief on added value for all value chain actors to use NUCs	Has not occurred yet.

Table 3. Outputs co-produced by all LLs in the first 2 years of the project

4.2 Living Lab by Living Lab

Having given a broad overview of what LLs collectively achieved over the past two years, the intent of this section is to provide more detailed information on WHAT each LL has co-produced per WP and HOW they have done it. Each LL sub-section is thus divided into two parts:

1. The first part called “Achievements” contains a table that provides more detailed information about WHAT each LL has co-produced and answers the first question laid out at the end of Section 3, i.e. *WHAT did the LL do in the first 2 years of the project?*
2. The second part called “Process”, answers the question “How have they done this?”, and articulates it in 3 sub-questions:
 - a. *Who was involved in the multi-stakeholder LL?* To show this, each part contains a table that shows the types of stakeholders (first column) involved in the LL per year (subsequent columns). The source for the information for October 2022 is the information contained in MS3 (Validation of LL plans) while the information for the last two columns comes from the posters prepared for the Annual Meetings (Portugal 2023 and Denmark-Sweden 2024 respectively). DIVINFOOD partners are indicated in bold.
 - b. How are stakeholders engaged, and participation stimulated and maintained?
 - c. How are new stakeholders recruited?

Bean-Cast

Achievements: What the LL did

WHAT did the LL do in the first 2 years of the project?

WP 1 - Diversify consumer-producer interactions to guide innovation in short and mid-tier chains and facilitate responsible consumption

The LL organised a face-to-face focus group discussion on lingot beans and the cassoulet with 9 citizens to collect their expectations and aversions regarding the use of agrobiodiversity in food chains, from breeding to marketing.

<p><i>WP 2 - Co-produce new and diversified healthy plant-based products and recipes</i></p> <p>NUC legume-based innovative recipes were developed, such as three organic/vegetarian cassoulet and 3 lingot bean vegetarian recipes (minestrone, croquetas and panna cotta). New recipes were demonstrated to consumers during workshops and fairs.</p>
<p><i>WP 3 - Co-develop ecosystem services-based agroecological farming systems</i></p> <p>Agroecological farming systems are tried out in experimental fields set by BIOCIVAM11 and a local agricultural school. The experiments explore effects of bio-stimulants and bio-inputs settings such as seed covering. For now, the trials can only be held with the available cultivars, but the most important technical gaps will come from farming new varieties (from WP4 work).</p> <p>A workshop was carried out to jointly decide which ecosystem services would be assessed out of a list of pre-selected ecosystem services and their indicators.</p>
<p><i>WP 4 - Co-breed under-utilized biodiversity for markets</i></p> <p>BIOCIVAM11, together with local partners set up a participatory breeding program. The first stages of cultivars characterisation and initial evaluations were done in volunteer citizens' gardens in the two first years of the projects. 10 varieties of lingot bean were chosen based on field trials carried out on the plots of 7 such volunteer gardeners and based on 3 criteria: agronomic, sanitary and quality.</p> <p>The cross-breeding and multiplication will then be done by vegetable/seed producers, and in experimental stations. Finally, once there are enough seeds, the beans will be introduced into farmers' cultivation plans.</p>

Table 4. Bean-Cast LL's achievements

Process: How the LL did it

Who was involved in the multi-stakeholder LL?

<i>Types of stakeholders</i>	<i>Up to October 2022</i>	<i>October 2022 – May 2023</i>	<i>May 2023 – June 2024</i>
Farms and other businesses	Several conventional bean producers Small scale cassoulet processors Cereal Cooperatives	+Seed producers +Cantine chefs	+Restaurants +Legume processors +Bio-input crafter
Municipality and other public institutions	Castelnaudary Municipality Community of communes Castelnaudary-Lauragais-Audois		

	Regional Tourist Development Institutions		
Citizens and community groups	Confrérie du Cassoulet (cultural association) Local gardeners' association	+Citizens (focus group WP1) +New gardeners	+Students
Local organisations and research	Agricultural schools Experts in breeding (INRAE) Institut Paul Bocuse Biocivam 11 (Coordinator)	+Researchers in beans (not just breeders abut also an ethnobotanist) +Union of (conventional) lingot bean farmers +Regional Legume Association	+Global Bean Network

Table 5. Bean-Cast LL's stakeholders

The LL has involved a multitude of stakeholders from the beginning. Stronger ties were established with some stakeholders compared to others based on the stage of the project activities and on interest. For example, stronger ties were built with the gardeners' association compared to some conventional bean producers due to the former's desire to experiment with organic seeds and methods from the beginning. A strong tie was also built with the Municipality of Castelnaudary, given the importance of the Cassoulet Festival for the local authorities and also in connection with their leading role in the 'Projet Alimentaire Territorial' (local food policy) of the community of communes, in which relocating bean production was set as a common objective. Agricultural schools were contacted from the beginning, but it was only in the second year that they were involved more strongly. This is for several reasons, one of them being that it is only in agricultural schools that it is possible to use large fields to experiment with growing beans organically, as opposed to small garden plots. Agricultural schools were also actively sought out as strategic partners by the LL Coordinator (Biocivam 11) due to the presence of students that represent possible future pathways for sustainable agriculture to grow, and due to their capacity to attract a wide variety of stakeholders when events are organised on their premises.

How are stakeholders engaged and participation stimulated?

Several methods were used to ensure engagement and participation. First, those stakeholders most involved in the project activities planned for the first two years (see table above) were engaged by carrying out the project activities themselves for which the same stakeholders had a strong interest and high levels of skills. For example, the Gardeners' Association decided to become part of DIVINFOOD specifically because they have a strong connection to the lingot bean – which is a heritage crop – and have a high interest in changing the current situation whereby most of the beans are produced using conventional methods. They are also very highly trained as they are almost all retired breeders or farmers. For this reason, keeping them engaged in technical work was a way to keep their interest high. For example, given the difficulty in growing lingot bean in the area, much work went into collectively identifying the main challenges in growing the bean in the Lauragais area, and in collecting resources and reviews about past experiences in lingot variety selection. Students were engaged by creating a course together with the Agricultural School on “participatory genetics selection” where students worked on the lingot beans.

Another way of keeping engagement levels high is by striking the right balance between meeting often enough to cover all the technical topics and coordination responsibilities envisaged by the project, but not too often to avoid “fatigue”.

The LL Coordinator also organised a series of longer face-to-face, thematic meetings with the intent of bringing stakeholders together around a theme of common interest, thus keeping engagement levels high. In fact, face-to-face meetings were preferred to online meetings specifically for that reason. The day long meetings also allowed for informal interactions and convivial situations such as eating together or sharing experiences, including visiting a processing factory, which ultimately helped bring people together.

How are new stakeholders recruited?

New stakeholders were recruited in a number of ways. Some of them were in the same meetings that were organised to bring together the LL stakeholders, i.e. longer face-to-face, thematic meetings. An example is a face-to-face meeting held on the topic of bean breeding, where new people were invited: breeders, small-scale farmers, hobby horticulturalists and representatives of a seed exchange forum.

The LL also organised awareness raising events, targeted mostly at citizens and using tools such as tastings, quizzes and recipe demonstrations. One such event occurred during the European Heritage Days (which takes place each year in September in European countries), in the town heritage museum, highlighting how agrobiodiversity is part of the cultural heritage of the citizens of the region.

The LL Coordinator also made efforts to link up the LL to international, European, national and regional networks/initiatives, both for visibility and to attract newcomers. This was the case of the (online) Global Bean Festival, for example. Newcomers here were the Mayor of Castelnaudary and new gardeners to be involved in citizen field trials. Links were also created with the Global Bean Network to recruit stakeholders for the “Community in Practice” around mild processing in legumes and cereals.

Bean-Lyon

Achievements: What the LL did

WHAT did the LL do in the first 2 years of the project?

WP 1 - Diversify consumer-producer interactions to guide innovation in short and mid-tier chains and facilitate responsible consumption

In the context of Task 1.1, in September 2022 the LL organised a focus group meeting with consumers on the “meat bean”. The LL organised the logistics of the event (venue, equipment needed, gifts/compensations for participants) and dealt with the selection and recruitment of

<p>a diverse set of consumers meeting the criteria (such as involvement, age, previous experience).</p>
<p><i>WP 2 - Co-produce new and diversified healthy plant-based products and recipes</i></p> <p>One chef produced the first meat bean recipe. Four other chefs were identified and invited to participate in order to perform the first cooking tests with meat beans and create recipes. A miller was involved in the project and produced a small quantity (about a kilo) of bean flour. This was distributed to pastry chefs.</p> <p>In September 2023, the very first National Sustainable Cuisine contest was set up by the Chef Christian Tetedoie and the Fondation Ginon in the Centre de Formation des Apprentis de la Gastronomie, in strong collaboration with the LL coordinator (mPmC) and with the support of some partners of DIVINFOOD (CRBA, INRAE). The main ingredient, for the 2023 contest, was the NUC meat bean, and active promotion of DIVINFOOD and of agrobiodiversity use in cooking was done.</p>
<p><i>WP 3 - Co-develop ecosystem services-based agroecological farming systems</i></p> <p>Trials of the mea” bean have been carried out in 5 organic farms with different types of land (soil), altitudes, and profiles to test the seeds under diverse agroecological farming systems. The trials are still ongoing and initial participatory assessment data is being collected.</p> <p>Thanks to the seeds harvested after the two years of experimentation but also thanks to the feedback of the producers, the meat bean cultivation was extended earlier than expected in the French Alps. In 2024, the LL increased the number of farms involved in meat bean cultivation to 14 farms in various territories (altitudes, soil type, etc.) and thus expanded the cultivation territory in the Auvergne-Rhône Alpes (AURA) region.</p> <p>In January 2024, LL AURA meat bean organised a focus group with DIVINFOOD farmers involved in the culture of the meat bean in order to share experience, techniques, etc. This focus group was combined with a participatory assessment of ecosystem services related to the use of agrobiodiversity managed by INRAE.</p>
<p><i>WP 4 - Co-breed under-utilised biodiversity for markets</i></p> <p>Under Task 4.2, the LL focused on producing enough seeds of the meat bean variety to be able to subsequently test it under different conditions (see WP 3 work above).</p>

Table 6. Bean-Lyon LL’s achievements

Process: How the LL did it

Who was involved in the multi-stakeholder LL?

<i>Types of stakeholders</i>	<i>Up to October 2022</i>	<i>October 2022 – May 2023</i>	<i>May 2023 – June 2024</i>
Farms and other businesses	5 farms mPmC	+3 farms +Mill Molinae	+6 farms +Terra Douceurs (processor)

		+Chef Tetedoie and others	
Municipality and other public institutions	Métropole de Lyon CFA Gastronomie (Centre de Formation des Apprentis) SMPMO (Syndicat Mixte Plaines et Mont d'Or)	+School canteen +Administrative canteen (RIL) +AURA Region +Chamber of Agriculture	+Ville de Chaponost agricultural high school +Parc Naturel Régional de Chartreuse
Citizens and community groups	Charézieux Nature Families	+Fondation Ginon +Fondation Pauline & Valérie Mercan	
Local organisations and research	CRBA (Centre de Ressources de Botanique Appliquée)		+A medical researcher

Table 7. Bean Lyon LL's stakeholders

Since its inception, the LL has expanded both in terms of including more members of the same category and in terms of new types of stakeholders. For example, initially the LL included 5 different (mostly small) organic farmers, with different types of land, altitudes, and agro-climatic profiles. The number then raised to 8 farms when enough seed was produced to share with the additional farms, one of which is a relatively large farm (130 ha). In this last year, efforts were made to include farms from other climatic areas, such as the mountainous (alpine) areas, so as to diversify the types of areas where the meat bean can be grown and sold. Chefs, located in Lyon and neighbouring areas, were contacted quite early in the development of the LL to raise their awareness of the initiative. Once enough product was available, they were more involved in the creation of recipes. Processors were also engaged: a mill and a processor who will start making cooked meat beans available for consumers in glass jars so as to facilitate their consumption.

Public institutions such as the Chamber of Agriculture, the AURA Region (Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes region) and representatives of the National Regional Park (Parc Naturel Régional de Chartreuse) were also contacted, but more efforts will be carried out in the next year to include these important stakeholders more fully in the LL. An important stakeholder that was contacted at the end of 2023 was the CEO of the public catering system of Lyon (Restaurant Inter-administratif de Lyon – RIL). The RIL prepares 1,300 meals per day and the objective of the LL is to convince the CEO to test NUC recipes, integrate them into their regular menus, and to work directly with farmers producing the meat bean).

An interesting addition in 2023 were two foundations, recruited through the mPmC network and the LL partners. Fondation Ginon for example is part of Chef Christian Tetedoie's network, while the Fondation Pauline & Valérie Mercan was brought in via CRBA's network. The foundations were recruited not so much for financial reason, but for their competencies: the Ginon Foundation for its competencies on sustainable cooking and the Pauline & Valérie Mercan Foundation for its focus on agrobiodiversity and health.

Efforts were made to include more researchers from within CRBA, and a presentation of the LL was made to the members of the INRAE Science and Participatory Research Direction to disseminate the work of the LL and potentially recruit more members into the LL. Finally, a researcher who works in oncology and is specialised in post-chemotherapy nutrition joined the LL to collaborate on the development of recipes with meat beans with the expectation that these will have good nutritional effects for post-chemotherapy patients.

How are stakeholders engaged and participation stimulated?

Participation in the various events and meetings organised, whether with all the LL or with some members, involved mainly traditional systems of oral presentations and an invitation/encouragement for everyone to share their ideas and comments. Social media (specifically the messaging system - OLVID) was used by a group of "sustainable cooks" with a view to share experiences on meat bean usage. Face-to-face meetings were used between CRBA and the farmers during field work, but were also almost always used with other stakeholders, especially with a view to convincing and persuading newcomers to join the LL. The European Heritage Days in September 2023 were also an opportunity for the CRBA to present meat bean to local stakeholders (over 300 participants).

How are new stakeholders recruited?

First and foremost, the LL Coordinator played a key role in contacting/visiting various new, at times "unconventional", stakeholders and inviting them to join the LL. His personal skills played an important role in convincing new stakeholders on board such as the chefs, larger farmers, millers and oncologists. These meetings were always conducted face-to-face and were sometimes aimed at introducing newcomers into the LL. Targeted awareness raising presentations of the LL and of DIVINFOOD to specific groups/stakeholders were also organised to inform and showcase what the project does. Lastly, the LL organised a very large public event with the Foundation for Sustainable Cuisine – the very first National Sustainable Cuisine contest – to raise awareness of the NUC with all stakeholders, and especially cooks and citizens. The contest was held among well-known chefs who prepared recipes using the meat bean and the press was invited to publicise the event widely.

Cer-Occ

Achievements: What the LL did

WHAT did the LL do in the first 2 years of the project?

WP 1 - Diversify consumer-producer interactions to guide innovation in short and mid-tier chains and facilitate responsible consumption

The LL organised a face-to-face focus group discussion on einkorn with 10 citizens to collect their expectations and aversions regarding the use of agrobiodiversity in food chains, from breeding to marketing.

WP 2 - Co-produce new and diversified healthy plant-based products and recipes

The processing partner PURPAN (affiliated third party of INRAE) developed and tested new NUC-based products. They conducted a technological and chemical analysis and also organised some consumer feedback sessions.

The LL had previous experience with crafting NUC flour and making pasta and bread. With DIVINFOOD they took some steps forward in evaluating different cultivars' quality within the products (e.g. pasta made with 6 pure cultivars of einkorn). They also developed some novel products such as bulgur, and then optimised and transferred the process to small-scale processors in Autumn 2023.

Beginning 2024: initial trials of einkorn and rivet wheat semolina.

WP 3 - Co-develop ecosystem services-based agroecological farming systems

Cer-Occ was very active in Task 3.4 concerning on-farm storage and pre-processing. In addition to collection of data on on-farm storage and pre-processing (current practices, innovations and difficulties) with an aim to provide the data for Deliverable 3.6, it organised a demonstration day to show different methods of sorting cereals. The event, which included a visit of a company offering sorting services and a demonstration of a mobile collective sorter, attracted over 90 participants. The LL Coordinator also explored ancient grain storage techniques with archaeologists. They partnered with an agricultural school to assess the feasibility of these methods in modern farming environments and to collect data on the efficiency of underground grain storage.

A field day/workshop was organised to carry out a participatory landrace evaluation and to jointly decide which ecosystem services would be assessed out of a list of pre-selected ecosystem services and their indicators. In 2024, some intercropping practices were tried out in field trials.

WP 4 - Co-breed under-utilised biodiversity for markets

BIOCIVAM11 coordinated the network of trial stations involving 19 varieties of einkorn, and 10 varieties of rivet wheat within 4 stations (research centers, and agricultural schools).

In 2023, the LL organised participatory sessions to define the breeding criteria. The LL decided to focus on 6 criteria: yield, precocity, resistance to disease, quality (taste), resistance to lodging, and competition to weeds. Based on these criteria, in 2024 the LL initialized some cross breeding activities.

Table 8. Cer-Occ LL's achievements

Process: How the LL did it

Who was involved in the multi-stakeholder LL?

<i>Types of stakeholders</i>	<i>October 2022</i>	<i>October 2022 – May 2023</i>	<i>May 2023 – June 2024</i>
Farms and other businesses	Farmers Bakers Small scale pasta processors	+Mill constructors +Local bakers' associations +Retailers +Another small local processor (Odyssee Engrain)	+Seed producers
Municipality and other public institutions	Occitania Region Public co-financers (FantaSCIC)		+Montpellier Metropole
Citizens and community groups	Students Citizens (interested in gluten-free products)	+Local associations	
Local organizations and research	INRAE and PURPAN Montpellier SupAgro Biocivam 11 (Coordinator)	+ Other researchers of INRAE and PURPAN (e.g., IATE Technological group) +Other agricultural schools +Baking Schools	+Archaeologists +FNAB (organic agriculture) network

Table 9. Cer-Occ LL's stakeholders

Compared to Bean-Cast, which is an emerging network or body of partners, Cer-Occ builds on a more longstanding network of a diversified set of stakeholders and can thus be considered as being at a more advanced stage. The largest change which has occurred in the past year as part of its involvement with DIVINFOOD is that of having engaged more with agricultural schools, in line with what happened in Bean Cast. In the case of the PURPAN School of Engineering, that has a number of courses specialised in agriculture, the added value of working with the school was that of having access to processing machineries for pre-processing and processing trials, but also that of being a venue considered as "legitimate" both in the eyes of actors using non-conventional methods, as well as those using them. In view of recruiting a larger number of conventional farmers, organising trainings and other events in the School/s was thus considered as strategic.

How are stakeholders engaged and participation stimulated?

Given that both this LL and Bean-Cast are coordinated by Biocivam 11, similar methods of engagement and participation were used as those discussed above. As before, the LL Coordinator organised a series of longer face-to-face meetings with the intent of bringing stakeholders together around a theme of common interest, thus keeping engagement levels high, and here too face-to-face meetings were preferred to online meetings specifically for that reason. An example is the annual meetings of the LL in 2023 and 2024 that coincided with the celebration of 'forgotten cereals'. The day-long meetings allowed for informal interactions and convivial situations, such as eating together einkorn and river wheat products or sharing experiences, such as participatory

landrace evaluations and a series of workshops in the afternoon on NUCs product development and marketing. Two one-day trainings were organised in Carcassonne on small-scale farm mills made of stone, involving farmers, processors and researchers.

How are new stakeholders recruited?

New stakeholders were recruited in the above-mentioned day-long events and trainings where newcomers were also welcome. Targeted events were also organised specifically to build new ties, such as the meeting with Agricultural Professional School of Toulouse Auzeville aimed at introducing the School to DIVINFOOD’s objectives and activities, or the meeting with PURPAN and the INRAE-IATE Technological Group where students were recruited to work on specific DIVINFOOD activities and where a local small processing firm came to know about the project through its links with the other actors invited. Specific windows of opportunity were also taken by the LL Coordination, such as involving the PURPAN School more deeply when the new Director, who expressed the wish to engage with new projects, came on board.

GPea-Port

Achievements: What the LL did

WHAT did the LL do in the first 2 years of the project?

WP 1 - Diversify consumer-producer interactions to guide innovation in short and mid-tier chains and facilitate responsible consumption

In October 2022, the LL organised a consumer focus group on grass pea using face-to-face and online meetings with 11 consumers.

WP 2 - Co-produce new and diversified healthy plant-based products and recipes

Innovative fermented products, namely grass pea miso and tempeh, were developed using Ancient Eastern-like methods. The LL organised a hands-on one-day workshop on, “How to make grass pea miso”, mainly developed and delivered by Cooking Lab. Small processors received training on how to make grass pea miso.

In terms of quality evaluations, raw seed from 15 grass pea Portuguese and one French landraces and processed seed (boiled, miso and tempeh) from one Portuguese landrace, were obtained and analysed for bioactive compounds using spectroscopy and wet chemistry methods. Very promising low-cost spectroscopic prediction models were developed for an anti-nutritional factor (ANF) content (beta-ODAP).

WP 3 - Co-develop ecosystem services-based agroecological farming systems

During the first year, three different grass pea varieties (two traditional white seed varieties, differing in seed size, one big and one small, and an exotic black seed variety) were selected and trialed in a participatory way. The LL compared sole crop with different innovative intercropping designs and with 3 different minor cereals (spelt, einkorn and rivet wheat). They were tested in 4 different farms with different agroecological conditions. Following

farmers’ concerns, the second-year field trials included also 4 different farms but changed focus to the comparison of alternative systems for a more sustainable weed management (using different interline distances, with and without mobilisation, and with and without herbicide application).
<i>WP 4 - Co-breed under-utilised biodiversity for markets</i>
Three varieties of grass pea were selected for multiplication and production following a participatory field evaluation to compare exotic (black seed) with local (white seed) germplasm. A cross breeding scheme with selected grass pea accessions has already undergone two cycles (two years of controlled crosses) to generate segregating materials to be tested through a participatory approach. The accessions were selected based on a number of criteria including seed size, colour, yield, disease resistance and quality related traits (protein and ANF contents) which were confirmed as important by LL stakeholders. The spectroscopic models developed in WP2 for the ANF content screening will be very helpful on the participatory selection of the segregating generated materials.

Table 10. GPea-Port LL’s achievements

Process: How the LL did it

Who was involved in the multi-stakeholder LL?

<i>Types of stakeholders</i>	<i>October 2022</i>	<i>October 2022 – May 2023</i>	<i>May 2023 – June 2024</i>
Farms and other businesses	3 small local farmers 2 processors	+ 1 processor + Alvaiázere Municipality’s farm	+ 1 farmer
Municipality and other public institutions	Alvaiázere Municipality		
Citizens and community groups	Confraria do Chícharo (Grasspea Fraternity)		
Local organisations and research	UNL ADECA (Alvaiázere Integrated Development Association) Cooking Lab	+ University of Évora	+ETP Sicó (the local technical high school)

Table 11. GPea-Port LL’s stakeholders

The LL is made up of actors that are geographically close, except for the researchers who are based in Lisbon and Évora. In spite of the researchers’ distance, all partners along the grass pea value chain have been included in the development of the chain itself. In this stage of the project, LL activities have rotated prevalently around farmers’ fields, although interactions with processors have been crucial to better understand what type of seeds to focus on. For example, the fact that there is a growing demand by processors of grass pea flour has led farmers to prefer the small

seed that has a thinner peel and can be more easily peeled and transformed into flour than a larger seed. Local organisations have played a key role in linking the researchers with the farmers, especially ADECA. The Municipality has supported the researchers mainly by allowing them to use a plot located in the centre of Alvaiázere for the researchers to carry out experiments and trials.

How are stakeholders engaged and participation stimulated?

The LL builds on a longstanding engagement of the UNL research team with the stakeholders present in Alvaiázere, which has allowed them to build trust and commitment to work together. The capacity of the research team to have a true dialogue with farmers and to take into consideration the point of view of the farmers when assessing different types of seed characteristics has helped keep farmers engaged because they see the benefit of continuing to participate in the project. An added incentive for the farmers to participate is the desire to find solutions to cultivating grass pea that will entice younger farmers to keep growing the crop. This inter-generational collaboration helps keep both older and younger farmers on board. Processors also see the benefit of working on the project as the project has worked to make the incorporation of the grass pea in diversified products easier. It has done so by developing innovative yet easier ways of processing, for example through fermentation, whereby the flour of fermented seeds is used to make pastries and other bakery products.

In terms of management techniques, the LL coordination team makes an effort to keep the momentum of project activities while avoiding stakeholder “fatigue” – especially of farmers - by taking up too much of their time. Meetings are staggered in time so as to avoid fatigue. With processors the risk of fatigue is lower, and this group of stakeholders is engaged through dedicated activities of interest to them, such as technical workshops on different ways of processing grass peas.

Although not yet directly involved in the project if not through the focus groups envisaged by WP1, citizens are also engaged in several ways. The plot made available by the Municipality of Alvaiázere and located in the centre of the town attracts citizens. UNL also has a field near its headquarters in Lisbon where it carries out NUC trials. Here, neighbourhood citizens actively participate by lending a hand or simply coming by to observe the results of the trials with this unknown crop for many.

Engagement is also stimulated by the fact that all stakeholders feel that they are learning through the project activities. The research team for example learn about new diseases/pests or about how to tackle climate change by their constant dialogue with farmers. For junior researchers the project is a way to interact with farmers rather than spending their time exclusively in the laboratory.

Farmer participation is mostly stimulated by traditional methods such as telephone conversations to organise meetings and face-to-face meetings. Citizen engagement, on the other hand, is stimulated through social media (Twitter and Facebook), and by trying to involve them directly in the activities of the project, such as through the field trials near Lisbon.

How are new stakeholders recruited?

The LL has not recruited many newcomers in the past two years as it has focused its attention on strengthening ties with longstanding partners and facilitating links between these and the project

stakeholders. A new processor- a pastry shop owner - was recruited thanks to the workshop on fermentation as she was interested in acquiring knowledge on other products based on grass pea that she could use in her recipes. In 2024 a new farmer joined the project based on discussions with the current farmers who are part of the project. He participated in the meeting that presented the results of the 2023 trials and planned the 2024 field trials.

Leg-ItSwitz

Achievements: What the LL did

WHAT did the LL do in the first 2 years of the project?

WP 1 - Diversify consumer-producer interactions to guide innovation in short and mid-tier chains and facilitate responsible consumption

The LL organised an online focus groups with 12 consumers from Italy dedicated to collect citizen-consumers' expectations and aversions regarding the use of lupins.

FiBL (Swiss sub-LL facilitator) participated to an event dedicated to promoting grass pea use in recipes in a restaurant in Zurich. During the event, participants (citizens) had the opportunity to learn about grass pea cultivation and lupin breeding, as well as about the lupin-based food products already on the market. The event included a tasting of chocolate with lupin a dinner in the host restaurant with a menu including grass pea-based recipes.

WP 2 - Co-produce new and diversified healthy plant-based products and recipes

Innovative fermented products are being developed out of lupin by CREA in Italy: white lupin/cow milk ricotta cheese or white lupin/cereal liquid yogurt (w/ gluten free version). Innovative foods are also being developed: bakery products (biscuits, cream crackers and bread) with bread wheat/einkorn or rice/maize and white lupin flour.

Easy to apply, low-cost quality evaluation tools for NUCs raw materials, based on spectrophotometry and spectroscopy, started to be developed for anti-nutritional and health beneficial compounds in white lupin seed; a spectrophotometer-aided, non-destructive selection tool for quinolizidine alkaloids (QAs) in white lupin was set up in the LL. This tool is able to discriminate between high (bitter) and low (sweet) QAs materials (seeds), but not among low QAs materials.

More artisanal pathways are being explored by the LL participants in Central Italy: lupin hummus is becoming a consolidated recipe appreciated by consumers in direct sale, while explorations are being carried out with different versions of sweet and salty creams.

In Switzerland, FiBL provided 6 commercial food producers (large, medium and small) with white lupin grain material with known alkaloid analysis (commercial cultivar Frieda, multiplied in the buffer of the field trial each year). The companies provided feedback to FiBL regarding

<p>the key quality requirement for the raw material for the target products and the suitability of the organic Swiss produced grain provided for the tests.</p>
<p><i>WP 3 - Co-develop ecosystem services-based agroecological farming systems</i></p> <p>The Italian LL participants discussed and prioritised ecosystem services delivered by white lupins during an online session. The grid will guide part of the agroecological performance assessment. In addition, the Farmers Field School methodology (SUSTAINET EA, 2010) was adopted to animate a LL meeting in Tuscany and to stimulate learning among participants: key agricultural and plant development moments were analysed to evaluate the growing season and to share good practices among farmers, advisors and researchers.</p> <p>The Swiss LL discussed and prioritised ecosystem services delivered by white lupins during a dedicated session in the end of the year event of the “Swiss Protein Power Network” on 1st December 2023.</p> <p>Four farms were involved to plan field trials in 2024 and two trials have been implemented successfully. About 10 organic farms across Switzerland are involved in monitoring the effect of agro-environmental variables on alkaloid accumulation. Lupin growers are provided (upon request) with free advice on agronomic practices by FiBL staff (by phone and email).</p>
<p><i>WP 4 - Co-breed under-utilised biodiversity for markets</i></p> <p>In Switzerland, field days to present white lupin breeding activities were organised in 2022, 2023 and 2024. In the field days in 2023 and 2024, a simple co-evaluation workshop was held to show the potential for participatory selection.</p> <p>In Italy, CREA tested a wide range of breeding lines to assess abiotic resistance (cold and drought), yields and alkaloid content. A CREA developed variety has been tested in a farm in Southern Tuscany to check both adaptation to the territory and alkaloid content in those specific pedo-climatic conditions. Local ecotypes (heritage varieties) are being adopted in both Tuscany and Marche regions in a functional relationship with the regional seed banks.</p>

Table 12. Leg-ItSwitz LL’s achievements

Process: How the LL did it

Who was involved in the multi-stakeholder LL?

<i>Types of stakeholders</i>	<i>Up to October 2022</i>	<i>October 2022 – May 2023</i>	<i>May 2023 – June 2024</i>
Farms and other businesses	<p><i>Switzerland</i> Several organic farmers 1 mill/ collection centre</p>	<p><i>Italy</i> +4 farms</p> <p><i>Switzerland</i> +2 farms directly interested in on-farm trials</p>	<p><i>Italy</i> +4 farms</p> <p><i>Switzerland</i> +2 processors (making tests)</p>

	2 organic seed and breeding companies 1 processor making test	+3 processors (making tests)	>10 farmers providing grain for alkaloid monitoring +1 farmers starting white lupin cultivation (on-farm trial)
Municipality and other public institutions	<i>Switzerland</i> Min Agriculture	<i>Italy</i> +Terre di Toscana	
Citizens and community groups	<i>Italy</i> Vegan Association (V-label Italia) <i>Switzerland</i> CH network “protein power”		<i>Switzerland</i> +1 farmers’ association
Local organizations and research	<i>Italy</i> CREA (National Research Centre on Agricultural Economics) FIRAB (LL Coordination) University of Pisa <i>Switzerland</i> FiBL (Organic Research Centre) Agroscope (Swiss research institute of Agriculture), as partner of the sister project CROPDIVA	<i>Italy</i> +Comunità del Cibo della Maremma (The Food Community of the Maremma) +Verdi Ambiente e Società CREA Regione Marche	<i>Italy</i> +Legambiente (Green Association) +Rete Semi Rurali (Seed research and advocacy group)

Table 13. Leg-ItSwitz LL’s stakeholders

Similarly to the case of the Nordic Labs illustrated above, the special characteristic of this Lab is that it includes actors that are based in two countries: Switzerland and Italy, in this case. The activities in the Swiss portion of the LL are facilitated by the FiBL research centre, while in Italy, activities take place in two geographically distinct yet thematically connected areas. In Northern Italy, due to the greater engagement of the CREA research centre, the focus is on breeding and processing, while activities in Central Italy hinge around the construction of a lupin value chain spearheaded by a number of interested farmers who use a mix of landraces and improved lupin varieties (including the variety produced by the CREA). The link between the three subgroups (Swiss, North and Central Italian) is ensured by the common aim of developing knowledge and practices around lupins, which are regularly exchanged and used to improve each other’s activities.

While the Swiss and Northern Italian portion of the LL has remained relatively stable in the past 2 years, the Central Italian sub-team has seen its members increase. The core of the sub-team

hinges around the farmers who form part of the Food Community of southern Tuscany (Maremma) with an aim to piggy back upon and leverage an existing entity supported by the regional government to foster greater agrobiodiversity in the Region. Given the strong similarity of objectives between DIVINFOOD and the Community, it seemed only natural to share resources and knowledge to support and expand an ongoing effort.

In Italy, meetings are currently held more frequent between farmers in Central Italy due to the stage at which the project is. Loose ties have been created with potential processors and retailers who can give value to the cultivated lupins, but have not been consolidated yet.

Links are instead maintained with the Northern sub-team of the LL through the work of the LL Coordinator, and through biannual joint meetings. Given the different segments of the value chain that the two sub-team are working on (the breeding and processing stage in the North and farming in the Centre), there is only a limited motivation for the whole team to work more fully together – this moment will come at a later stage when the actors from Central Italy will be able to benefit from the findings of the Northern sub-team more fully, and the latter can benefit from the directions and feedback of the former. In the first case, the team from Central Italy can learn new ways of processing lupins, while the team from Northern Italy (working more closely with the research station) can get feedback from farmers actually using the seeds developed by the research team.

In Switzerland, the white lupin value chain network (breeding, farming, food production) is strongly connected with the national network for the cultivation of all grain legumes in the country (Protein Power Network, Legume Hub Suisse) in order to leverage the common base of actors interested in different minor pulses. Network and knowledge exchange activities with crop-specific focus (e.g. anthracnose management, alkaloid management) are developed specifically for white lupin growers and processors. The support in building the national value chain by additional co-funding of the Ministry of Agriculture and the organic farmers association BioSuisse, and the collaboration by an organic miller/ collector allows a wide outreach of the LL activities. Specific effort has been dedicated (workshop in February 2023, field day in July 2024) to expand the network in the French speaking part of Switzerland.

How are stakeholders engaged and participation stimulated?

Stakeholders' interest is maintained in a variety of ways, depending on who the stakeholders are and the activity/ies they are involved in. First and foremost, the personal contacts that the LL Coordinator keeps with the stakeholders are key to keep the momentum going. Secondly, farmers' engagement is kept high by focusing on agronomic themes that help them with the production of lupins, such as technical advice (e.g. field days, collective advice and individual consulting service).

An example is the Field Day that was organised in Tuscany at the beginning of 2024. The day gathered researchers and farmers who cultivate lupins in central Italy and activities used the Farmer Field School participatory methodology. Themes touched upon several stages of the value chain, from farm agronomic practices to the possible aggregation of harvests and collective interface with processors. More than 10 farmers participated, some of whom are more fully engaged in the LL, and others who came for the first time and were interested to learn more about lupins. Team building was strengthened by touching upon themes of strong interest to farmers, i.e. diversification of farm income through lupins, related new knowledge, and a community of practice with which to share results and practices.

The Swiss sub-team also organised a series of workshops to keep up with project activities to also foster engagement. Field days were organised with LL and external partners around themes such as legumes (e.g. Bio Legume Day 2023 and 2024), or day long workshops in the context of the Protein Power Network. Such days were open to a range of stakeholders and were a mix of technical seminars (on post-harvest management for example) and more awareness-raising/promotional activities aimed at making NUCs more visible to the general public.

How are new stakeholders recruited?

The above-mentioned days and events were used to attract new members of the LL, as were other more informal methods, such as word-of-mouth. It is to be noted that while some events were specifically organised to become acquainted with new lupin farmers – with adjacent regions in central Italy for example – this was done mostly to have a clearer map of the potential “lupin network” in a certain area and not so much to recruit new farmers. Making a map of current lupin growers was also the aim of the workshop on lupins organized in the context of Task 2.5 that concluded with the creation of a Whatsapp group for all lupin growers across the 7 DIVINFOOD countries that participated. Recruiting new members in Italy and Switzerland is a step that will be left for a future moment, given the current difficulty of supporting a wide range of geographically dispersed farmers.

Leg-Hung

Achievements: What the LL did

WHAT did the LL do in the first 2 years of the project?

WP 1 - Diversify consumer-producer interactions to guide innovation in short and mid-tier chains and facilitate responsible consumption

A focus group discussion with a diverse group of representatives of the short legume value chain (farmers, retailers, restaurants, researchers) was organised in October 2022 in the frame of the 11th Forum “Let’s liberate diversity” in Budapest.

WP 2 - Co-produce new and diversified healthy plant-based products and recipes

Under SVÉT's guidance, experiments of food products and recipes with diverse legumes and minor cereals from the farmers involved in the LL took place in 12 premium restaurants in Hungary, representing a total of 32 individual food experiments (including 4 bread experiments). In 2024 the collaboration with restaurants expanded to restaurants outside the SVÉT network and a few gastro-bloggers who produced a series of recipes. Also, some meals/recipes were created outside of SVÉT events, e.g. a pop-up at one of the farmers’ markets in Budapest in the beginning of May.

WP 3 - Co-develop ecosystem services-based agroecological farming systems

<p>Altogether 19 varieties of 5 legume species were tested in 2022 and 23 varieties of 6 legume species were tested in 2023, respectively, on 5 small organic vegetables farms, 1 organic arable land farm and 1 regenerative arable land farm. In 2023 the focus was more on producing sufficient quantities for kitchen testing, so larger surfaces were involved. Guidance for cultivation was provided and data collection was done with a pre-prepared template. The number of on-farm experimental sites continued to increase in 2024, both for horticultural and field trials. This is also due to the cooperation with ÖMKI for joint data collection and sharing.</p> <p>A workshop was carried out in September 2023 to jointly decide which ecosystem services would be assessed out of a list of pre-selected ecosystem services and their indicators.</p>
<p><i>WP 4 - Co-breed under-utilised biodiversity for markets</i></p> <p>In September 2023 a selection of interesting legume varieties was carried out by a group of farmers and researchers. The criteria used to choose the varieties were stable yields, promising and worthy of propagation, uniqueness and commercial availability.</p>

Table 14. Leg-Hung LL’s achievements

Process: How the LL did it

Who was involved in the multi-stakeholder LL?

<i>Types of stakeholders</i>	<i>October 2022</i>	<i>October 2022 – May 2023</i>	<i>May 2023 – June 2024</i>
Farms and other businesses	8 small producers (gardeners) 1 larger, professional producer (arable land) 1 short food supply chain (SFSC) retailer	+2 SSC retailers +Szentesi Mag – seed retail company +7 restaurants	+3 small producers (gardeners) +7 farmers (2 with access to a mill and a processing facility)
Municipality and other public institutions	Budapest Municipality National Centre for Biodiversity and Gene Conservation	+Ministry of Agriculture (State Secretariat for Agriculture and Rural Development) +National Chamber of Agriculture	
Citizens and community groups	Association of Stylish Rural Restaurants (SVÉT) MagHáz Association – Community Seed Bank Association of Conscious Consumers (ACC)	+Former EIP-AGRI Operational Group on food legume cultivation +Gastro-bloggers	+Heroes of Responsible Dining (NGO)

Local organisations and research	Agri Kult and ÖMKI ESSRG (Environmental Social Science Research Group) (sister project RADIANT partner)	+Institute of Agricultural Economics +University of Debrecen – Institutes for Agricultural Research and Educational Farm	
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Table 15. Leg-Hung LL’s stakeholders

Over the course of two years the LL has grown. More farmers have become involved in the project, particularly larger arable farms. While arable farmers provide fewer opportunities to experiment with special varieties (as they prefer to use tried and tested commercial varieties), when they accept to do so, they present the opportunity to produce larger quantities for kitchen trials, consumer evaluation, and sale in restaurants and shops, which is a key objective of the LL. An important step forward has been that of including farmers who have access to mills and processing facilities, as this allows to overcome the logistics blockage. The missing actor among farmers and other rural businesses are seed providers. Contacts have been made with seed retailers to understand what it would take for some of the LL farmers to become seed suppliers. A group of actors that are showing a growing interest in the project are restaurants, even those who do not belong to the partner SVÉT but that have legumes on their menu and would like to find reliable sources of material, and rarely used species/varieties. Similarly, the LL has been quite successful in contacting gastro bloggers who can create recipes from the legumes grown in the LL and also share some content on this with their followers.

The LL built on the good relationships forged through previous projects and partnerships with some of the partners listed in Columns 1 and 2, such as the Ministry of Agriculture, the research institutions, the Gene Bank, and some of the restaurants and SFSC retailers.

How are stakeholders engaged and participation stimulated?

Several methods are used to engage stakeholders while at the same time avoiding “fatigue”. Generally, face-to-face meetings facilitate engagement. However, given the geographical spread of the LL however, including farms, restaurants and other actors dislocated over the country, the LL coordination team has organised both face-to-face and online meetings. The latter are easier to carry out and thus facilitate engagement.

As for the size of the group, depending on the stakeholder, the LL has at times used group meetings to facilitate engagement or one-on-one. For some stakeholders that are particularly hard to engage with because of the amount of time they work, such as chefs, the team has met with them regularly on a one-to-one basis, while with others, it has been easier to organize group meetings, such as with farmers and other rural actors such as breeders. In this last case, meetings were organised around themes of interest to farmers, such as legume cultivation technology – chefs were not invited to the latter, given the theme.

In the case of farmers, the LL has, over the last year, devoted more time to visiting farmers one by one, both to collect data - which is otherwise difficult to get farmers to do in season - to talk to them in person about the year, their experiences, and their plans.

Engagement and participation are also stimulated through trainings through the use of social media, such as the farmer WhatsApp group where farmers exchange useful information on where

to source seed for example. In physical and online meetings, engagement was stimulated by asking certain participants to present their work, and then stimulating a debate/conversation.

How are new stakeholders recruited?

Several methods were used to favour recruitment and engagement. Word-of-mouth and personal contacts were used extensively. The latter was particularly effective for recruiting a larger farmer who was willing to grow lentils and chickpeas on 2.5 acres. This may be considered as a success considering the difficulty of producing enough material for kitchen trials and consumer evaluation. Word of mouth was used by farmers to recruit new farmers, or to recommend new farmers to the LL Coordination team who then invited them themselves.

Recruitment through LL partners was another method used, as in the case of chefs recruited thanks to SVET, or the engagement of restaurants outside SVET recruited by other partners such as farmers. Workshops and trainings were also a useful venue for recruiting newcomers. This was the case of farmers and breeders who were recruited through training workshops on legume cultivation technology. Lastly, Facebook and other social media were used to recruit new members as well as more “traditional” forms of communication, such as SVET’s magazine, which is distributed to all its members (about 30).

Cer-Hung

Achievements: What the LL did

WHAT did the LL do in the first 2 years of the project?

<p><i>WP 1 - Diversify consumer-producer interactions to guide innovation in short and mid-tier chains and facilitate responsible consumption</i></p> <p>A face-to-face focus group discussion with 15 consumers on einkorn was organised in 2022 in the frame of the Soul of Bread Festival in Budapest.</p>
<p><i>WP 2 - Co-produce new and diversified healthy plant-based products and recipes</i></p> <p>A series of new products were developed including 3 types of pastas and bread made of emmer, einkorn and spelt. These were then evaluated through a community-based consumer approach, involving 25 consumers (pasta products) and through bread tasting at ‘Soul of the Bread’ Festival</p>
<p><i>WP 3 - Co-develop ecosystem services-based agroecological farming systems</i></p> <p>In March 2024, a number of ecosystem services were chosen out of a list of pre-selected ecosystem services and their indicators. These are the services that will be assessed during the project life.</p> <p>On-farm trials were launched at 7 locations across Hungary in October 2022. Field trials were successfully carried out at 3 locations with one landrace and at 2 locations with more einkorn or emmer landraces.</p>

<p><i>WP 4 - Co-breed under-utilised biodiversity for markets</i></p> <p>In June 2023, OMKI organised a field day aimed at choosing a first list of interesting varieties. 2 varieties of einkorn and 2 of emmer were chosen based on a list of criteria including yield, seed shape and size and colour of the ear.</p> <p>In 2023, a participatory plant breeding approach for targeting farmers’ needs has continued based on OHMs of the EPO×DIC durum-emmer crosses. Seed production of emmer landraces and small plot trials with 2 emmer and 2 einkorn landraces were also successfully performed in three locations.</p>
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Table 16. Cer-Hung LL’s achievements

Process: How the LL did it

Who was involved in the multi-stakeholder LL?

<i>Types of stakeholders</i>	<i>October 2022</i>	<i>October 2022 – May 2023</i>	<i>May 2023 – June 2024</i>
Farms and other businesses	2 farmers Artisanal millers Pasta makers Artisanal bakers	+3 farmers	+5 farmers -One of the pasta makers closed down +Artisan Bakers Association
Municipality and other public institutions	Budapest Municipality Matrica Museum and Archaeological Park	+National Food Chain Safety Office +Ministry of Agriculture	+National Centre for Biodiversity and Gene Conservation
Citizens and community groups	ACC (Association of Conscious Consumers) AgriKulti		
Local organisations and research	OMKI (LL Coordinator) ATK (Centre for Agricultural Research)	+ESSRG (Environmental Social Science Research Group) +Nebih - experimental Station	+ Institute of Agricultural Economics +Kisleptek Association (NGO working on local production)

Table 17. Cer-Hung LL’s stakeholders

The Cer-Hung LL is an emerging LL that aims to revamp the cultivation and use of ancient cereals in Hungary. Thanks to the leadership of OMKI (the Hungarian Research Institute of Organic Agriculture), it builds on a good network of farms that OMKI has already worked with and with a good network of contacts with other actors along the value chain. In this respect, the creation of a farmer-miller-baker database and the organization of workshops that bring these actors together is an important feature of OMKI’s work. An example is the recent (November 2023) Farmer-Miller workshop that was organised in Martonvasar involving 17 participants to discuss the current situation and challenges in the production and use of organic wheat and ancient cereals in

Hungary, to assess the changing needs of market actors and to strengthen the cooperation between the actors in the emmer- einkorn supply chain.

In the DIVINFOOD project, OMKI started working with a few of farmers, the number now having grown to 5-10 farmers (the number is not fixed as some drop out for 1-2 years and will join later). OMKI's strategy is not to increase the number of farmers at present for two main reasons: the first is that OMKI itself does not have the resources to properly support more farmers, and the second is linked to the current economic crisis that the country is facing which does not encourage consumers to buy NUC-based organic products due to their higher price. In turn, this does not encourage farmers to invest in the NUCs value chain.

An important actor that the LL would like to attract are pre-processors and specifically dehullers. One of the weaknesses of the NUC value chain, especially for einkorn, is the lack of dehulling machines and low pre-processing capacity across the country. Rice dehullers can be adapted to dehull einkorn and emmer, but the problem is that there are few of them, and they are scattered around the country, which makes their accessibility difficult for farmers.

An important actor that was brought in from 2023 is the Committee within the Ministry of Agriculture in charge of the Hungarian Foodstuff Code. Work is underway with relevant members of the Committee to find ways to update some relevant mandatory regulations and guidelines related to sourdough. This would help to better communicate the value of sourdough products made with the LL NUCs and to thus boost sales.

How are stakeholders engaged and participation stimulated?

In this phase of the project, OMKI has worked more closely with farmers on seed selection, participatory breeding and field trials. Face-to-face meetings on technical matters with the farmers themselves have been a core part of OMKI's work. In addition to that, OMKI organised a series of face-to-face workshops on technical issues of interest to the farmers, such as cultivation techniques for emmer and einkorn, quality traits and visits to dehulling and milling facilities. Collaboration among stakeholders and joint work was encouraged, as for example during the workshop that was co-organised with ACC where a pasta maker was involved in consumer tasting sessions. Field days, tours and sharing meals also formed part of the team-building efforts. Citizens, in particular, were involved through festivals, fairs, field visits and online cooking workshops.

Face-to-face was the preferred method for communication and partner engagement, but social media such as Facebook and Instagram were also used. During the workshops and field visits, traditional methods like presentations followed by Q&A were used, but also more innovative facilitation methods such as World Café were used to facilitate mingling between different stakeholders.

How are new stakeholders recruited?

One of the difficulties of building a value chain for einkorn and emmer is the involvement of pre-processors and consumers. As we have seen above, dehulling (and milling) the harvested crop, in particular, is a problem due to the difficulty of finding pre-processors readily available across the country and due to the lack of small machines to be able to do the work. The strategy used by

OMKI to recruit pre-processors and processors is that of using wheat as an “entry point” to foster joint work and introduce the NUCs.

Given the importance of wheat for all stakeholders across the value chain this is also used as an “entry point” in training aimed at millers and bakers, with an aim (also) to capture new stakeholders willing to try out NUCs using organic methods. For example, training were organised on quality traits of cereals, where information was provided both on wheat and on NUC cereals. Another strategy used to attract new farmers, but also other actors, is that of organising field visits in areas of the country where OMKI works with few farmers or with non NUC crops, with a view to work with farmers on NUCs – and therefore make NUC products available - all over the country.

Attracting consumers is viewed as one the biggest constraints to the development of the NUCs value chains. A number of tools are used to attract consumers, fairs and festivals amongst them. For example, the 2023 sourdough bread festival focused on einkorn: there was a roundtable discussion on the health benefits of einkorn and an einkorn bread competition for professional bakers, attracting a large number of visitors. Bread tasting for visitors was organised by the LL to attract consumers through tasting and tips on appealing ways to use NUC flours into home-made cooking, such as the suggestion of using a small amount of NUC flour into home-made bread, rather than only using a NUC flour which may sound unappealing to consumers unaccustomed to this type of flour. Another tool, an interactive map “Best places to buy - Emmer and einkorn shops on the map!”, was also developed to help consumers find their nearest local producers and shops more easily and made the map available on OMKI’s webpage.

In spite of the limitations linked to encouraging more farmers to grow NUCs, OMKI has used field visits to landrace trials in different parts of the country to showcase the work being done and engage with new partners, including new farmers who may be interested in NUCs.

Another strategy to attract more partners in the LL is to develop the Farmer-Miller-Bakers network which at the moment is more of a database. To this end, OMKI is organising a cereal festival in June 2025 together with the members of this network with a view to strengthening their links and to strengthen the network itself.

Faba-Nord and Leg-Nord

The information below concerns two distinct LLs: one is larger, focused on faba bean, and works with larger, industrial actors (Faba-Nord), while the other is smaller, considers a wider diversity of legumes and works on direct sales/short food chains (Leg-Nord). Although these LLs are distinct, we are however presenting their data together as there is a very close tie and several overlaps between the activities of the two. For example, both are emerging, deal with legumes and work across borders.

Achievements: What the LLs did

WHAT did the LLs do in the first 2 years of the project?

<p><i>WP 1 - Diversify consumer-producer interactions to guide innovation in short and mid-tier chains and facilitate responsible consumption.</i></p> <p>The LLs organised two face-to-face focus groups with 8 and 7 consumers respectively dedicated to collecting citizen-consumers' expectations and aversions regarding the use of faba beans, grey peas, lentils and blue lupins.</p>
<p><i>WP 2 - Co-produce new and diversified healthy plant-based products and recipes.</i></p> <p>In terms of quality evaluation, the grain legumes of the 2 LLs were analysed with chefs (under Nordvara's guidance) to assess their sensorial qualities and technical properties. This was done in order to pick out candidates for the development of new grey peas and lentils' recipes.</p> <p>In addition to this, a nutritional analysis (e.g. phytic acid) of raw NUC legume materials was also carried out, as well as a safety analysis of processed NUCs, particularly for mold and toxins.</p>
<p><i>WP 3 - Co-develop ecosystem services-based agroecological farming systems.</i></p> <p>Denmark: On-farm trials with lentils were planned and conducted on two locations (Bornholm and Djursland). The trials included varieties of interest for both Danish and Swedish farmers, and for varieties with small seeds, a higher plant density was tested. Due to a very dry period in May the plants did not recover the mechanical weed control resulting in a too low plant density and too much weed. Both trials were discarded before harvest and the varieties are being tested again in 2024.</p> <p>Sweden: In the season of 2023, field trials were performed in collaboration with SLU to test and document the performance of different cultivars of grey pea and of grey pea intercropped with several cultivars of faba bean.</p> <p>Data collection for on-farm storage and pre-processing: discussion with a small group of Danish growers and processors on the challenges and solutions for cleaning lentils.</p>
<p><i>WP 4 - Co-breed under-utilised biodiversity for markets</i></p> <p>A multi-actor participatory co-evaluation workshop was held in Denmark with both LL stakeholders to choose a first list of interesting varieties of faba beans, grey peas, lentils and narrow leaved lupins. Relevant criteria used were the commercial availability of the seeds both in Denmark and Sweden, their agronomic adaptability and their taste and use by consumers.</p>

Table 18. Faba-Nord and Leg-Nord LLs' achievements

Process: How the LLs did it

Who was involved in the multi-stakeholder LLs?

<i>Types of stakeholders</i>	<i>October 2022</i>	<i>October 2022 – May 2023</i>	<i>May 2023 – June 2024</i>
Farms and other businesses	Farmers, processing and retail <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Various associations of farmers • Nordisk Ravara • Aurion • Linser for livet • Food Bornholm • Gl. Buurholm • Kragegaarden • Naturbruget Tranum Breeding and seed companies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nordic Seed • Quinoa Quality • Danish Agro 	Farmers, processing and retail + Svensk Fava	Farmers, processing and retail + new farmers + Bælgkompagniet Cooking + Grønning & Kjærgaard
Municipality and other public institutions	Danish Agriculture and Food Council Food Organization of Denmark	+The Swedish Food Academy	
Citizens and community groups	Educators The Danish Vegetarian Society (DVF)		
Local organisations and research	SLU ICOEL Ax Foundation/Future Food Project	+Copenhagen Hospitality College	

Table 19. Faba-Nord and Leg-Nord LLs' stakeholders

The LLs include actors from all four categories of actors. Depending on the NUC value chain, collaborations have been more intense between certain actors and less so with others. For example, in the case of lentils, a strong obstacle is linked to the production phase, given that weather conditions have not allowed the proper testing of the lentil varieties. Therefore, work is more intense with farmers on that front. With respect to the lupins and the faba bean, the obstacle is not so much in growing but in consumer knowledge/acceptability and pre-processing. In the case of the faba bean, the thick outer skin can make its cooking more difficult and therefore less acceptable to chefs and consumers, while for the lupin there is still work to do to remove the alkaloids that give a bitter taste. In this case, the interactions with processors have been key to learning about ways to make these two NUCs more marketable. Two training sessions were organised to share knowledge on NUCs processing, while two workshops were organised with a well-known chef to increase competencies on the use of the lupin in the kitchen.

The LL Coordinator has organised one LL meeting where all members from both countries come together. They call themselves “The Legume Alliance”, which shows the level of commitment and vision that the group has in terms of building sustainable NUC chains. It is in these contexts that

members from the different stakeholder groups can exchange information and learn from others. For example, farmers learn from organisations that are more in touch with consumers, such as the DVF, about the evolving tastes of consumers and what they need to put in place to cater to these new tastes. It is also an avenue where Swedish and Danish farmers, in spite of the differences in language, can share experiences about the NUCs they are growing. Another LL meeting for all partners was planned for spring 2024 but was cancelled because the farmers were too busy in the field. The project partners have regular meetings to exchange knowledge from the LL.

How are stakeholders engaged and participation stimulated?

All stakeholders involved in the LLs have a strong incentive to be part of the LLs. Recent years have seen an expansion of the market for vegetarian products which opens the door for the development of home-grown legumes. There is, therefore, an incentive for all stakeholders to come together and develop NUC legume value chains, and to learn from one another to better overcome key barriers that these value chains face, such as the few varieties adapted to a short growing season, the fact that faba bean is more known as feed and less as food, or the lack of suitable processing facilities.

The presence of a number of small and medium companies may at times lead to tensions due to the reluctance to share information about and disseminate the product resulting from patented or “branded” seeds, but overall, the desire to learn from one another and to build vibrant value chains prevails. In this process, the engagement of public-private organisations and associations that provide a platform for dialogue and joint collaboration is important.

The LL Coordinator has maintained a balance between organising meetings between all stakeholders and avoiding “fatigue” by not organising too many. For this reason, the Leg-Nord LL is organised into smaller “thematic” clusters to facilitate efficient communication and collaboration, such as for example, a specific group on lentils that meets online every 2 months. This is also convenient due to the large size of the LL and the physical distance between stakeholders.

Initially, due to the size of the LL, the LL Coordinator had planned more online meetings, but many stakeholders expressed a desire for in-person gatherings, particularly the Swedish partners. This shows the high level of engagement of partners. English is used extensively in these meetings to overcome language barriers.

Maintaining communication and collaboration within the cluster of LLs is crucial to ensure alignment and prevent divergence in objectives and activities. Various communication channels are utilised to facilitate this, including emails, phone calls, and online platforms such as Teams. In Denmark, coordination often occurs through the LL coordinator, while in Sweden, organisations like SLU play a key role due to their extensive contacts and networks. In fact, they are de facto an informal LL coordinator of the Swedish partners. At an LL meeting held in 2023, the participants indicated that they would prefer physical meetings. However, after cancelling the meeting twice in spring 2024 due to the farmers being too busy, online solutions are looking more into. Recognising the need for quick and efficient communication, a WhatsApp or Facebook group is planned to address daily challenges promptly, whether in the kitchen or the field. Participants express a preference for immediate responses rather than waiting for scheduled Teams meetings. During the face-to-face meetings, facilitation techniques are used to keep interest levels high.

How are new stakeholders recruited?

In Denmark, farmers have a strong culture of knowledge sharing, both within and outside the project. They recognize the value of collaboration and are accustomed to an open system where sharing knowledge is commonplace. A number of new farmers have joined the LL in 2023-24. The only condition placed by LL stakeholders in recruiting new members is the actual involvement in NUC development to be able to share useful information for all. The LL is thus not open to auditors or people who are simply interested in NUCs. Training sessions and workshops, such as those organised by the chef Bille or for processors, are also other ways to capture new participants.

5. Discussion and conclusions

The above information offers a rich description of what the LLs have achieved both in terms of tangible results and in terms of the process followed to achieve those results. In this last section, we will not dwell on the former, as we believe that the latest Mid-Term Review (MTR) offers a comprehensive overview of what the LLs have produced in the first 18 months of their work. Due to the multi-disciplinary, multi-stakeholder and “whole value chain” approach of the project, we will however explore more in detail the process that they followed to get there and dwell more in particular on questions we asked ourselves at the beginning of this report, and which were stressed during the review of the first reporting period, such as: did the LLs involve a diversity of stakeholders and who are they? How were stakeholders engaged, how was participation stimulated, and, above all, maintained? How are new stakeholders recruited? In order to frame our analysis and “categorise” the types of strategies and tools used by the LLs, we will use the guidance given by Deliverable 5.1 (“Framework for LL facilitation and data production”) on engagement, participation and recruitment.

In terms of **stakeholder diversity**, the guidance was clear on including stakeholders belonging to all the stages of the NUCs value chain – from breeding to consumption, and, in doing so, to also think of the complementary and different roles in these areas: policy makers, private sector actors, associations, etc. In this respect, the table of stakeholders for each LL displayed in the previous section, shows that year by year each LLs was able to include stakeholders from each stage of the value chain and covering different roles. As we will see below, not all stakeholders were drawn in with the same level of intensity: with some stakeholders, the tie is stronger and more frequent while with others it is looser, even though they are all part of the LL and meet altogether at least once a year. Some LLs have reported that certain categories of stakeholders are somewhat missing due to contextual reasons (for example, there may be few cereal processors available in a given region) and that more work needs to be done to create or strengthen links with them.

In terms of **stakeholder engagement and participation**, two main areas of work were recommended by Deliverable 5.1: to carry out *engagement activities* such as open discussions, dialogues, field trips, and cooking shows, and to use a *mix of communication tools*.

All LLs organised a diverse array of *engagement activities* that can be categorised into four main groups. The first is made up of activities closely tied to project commitments under each WP, such as participatory eco-systems assessments, recipe development, field trials, etc. Participating in these events, whether with all other stakeholders, or with a limited number of them helped keep

the level of interest and engagement high simply because what attracted stakeholders to the project to begin with were the themes explored during these activities. Stakeholders could also see the benefit of taking part in these activities, which heightened their sense of engagement. The second set of activities was made up of large events open to a wide audience, such as the European Heritage Days, the Sourdough Festival in Hungary and the National Sustainable Cuisine contest in France, where the showcasing of the project's work through public display such as cooking demos, tastings and contests strengthens stakeholder motivations and commitment. The third set of activities, and one that was used by all LLs, are the field visits. This is closely related to the fourth group, which is the one made up of thematic workshops or trainings, as the field visits often also contain an element of training. Examples are the annual professional field days in Hungary, the lupin hackathon in Italy with students, the training on small-scale farm mills in France, or the workshop on the use of lupins in Denmark. There are various elements in these activities that help keep the engagement of stakeholders high, such as the knowledge that stakeholders acquire and the ties they consolidate, and in some cases build when there are newcomers. The convivial character of some of these activities, where there are shared meals and joint activities undertaken, helps to create a greater sense of team and engagement.

All LLs used a *mix of communication tools*, ranging from more “traditional” tools to those that use more electronic devices. The most preferred methods were the more traditional face-to-face methods. Even for those LLs where stakeholders are more geographically spread out, such as Hungary or the Nordic LLs, there was a preference to meet personally. When this did occur, traditional tools were used to exchange ideas and knowledge, such as PowerPoint presentations and facilitated discussions. Otherwise, LLs used a mix of online, face-to-face and hybrid methods to facilitate participation. WhatsApp and Teams were the preferred ways of communicating to set up meetings/have quick exchanges, in addition to simply calling stakeholders by phone. In addition to verbal exchanges, some LLs chose “experiential” ways of communicating, as in the case of Portugal, where the Municipality of Alvaiázere allowed researchers to use a plot located in the centre of the city to carry out experiments and trials that everyone could see and learn from. Above all, it is worth noting that the personal skills of the LL Coordinators play a key role in putting stakeholders in touch and providing constant ways of sharing and connecting.

In order to keep engagement high, Deliverable 5.1 recommended to identify and avoid *stakeholder “fatigue”*, and this is an aspect related to engagement that many LLs were aware of and acted to circumvent. A strategy often used to strike the right balance between engagement and avoiding fatigue was that of calibrating the timing and participation of meetings to avoid redundancy and excessive frequency. Meetings were thus staggered based on who was to attend or based on the type of value chain to work on. For example, in Hungary, fewer and separate meetings are held with chefs due to the little time available for this group of entrepreneurs, while in Italy and Portugal, where farming and processing activities are less connected at the moment, (mostly) separate meetings are held with these two types of actors to avoid one group losing interest if the meeting focuses on the topic of most interest to the other. The latter is also the rationale for the development of “thematic” clusters within the Nordic Labs, such as the lentils cluster that meets every two months. In the Nordic LLs, it is also the type of value chain that determines how meetings are calibrated: when discussing aspects related to lentils, it is farmers that are mostly called upon due to the fact that more attention needs to go to this portion of the value chain, while in the case of faba beans, it is processing – and the relative actors - that receives more attention.

Recruitment was another area of prominence for the project, aimed ultimately at helping LLs transform into more stable territorial networks. Deliverable 5.1 gave two relevant recommendations to encourage expansion: to identify and work with *multipliers*, such as community groups, professional organisations, student groups and local networks (public or private), and to identify and work with *influencers* such as local politicians, chefs, artists or prominent community figures. With respect to the former, several multipliers have been drawn into the LLs, thereby increasing the visibility and connection of the LL to a wider group of members. Examples are networks, such as the farmer-miller-baker network in Hungary, or the Protein Power network in Switzerland, communities of practice, such as the Food Community in the Tuscan Region in Italy, or schools, such as the agricultural schools in France that give access to a large number of students and the academic community overall. Influencers were involved to a lesser degree: chefs were among the main types of influencers brought in, together (in some cases) with prominent political figures or members of the medical community.

In addition to observing *who* was involved with an aim to expand the LL, it is interesting to also note what kinds of strategies/tools were used to draw new people in. Some of the strategies seen above that were used to engage stakeholders, also served the purpose of attracting new members, such as the large, open events or the field visits. Other actions relate to organising awareness raising presentations to targeted audiences or using popular themes to attract newcomers, such as organising trainings around a topic that is popular among farmers and then introducing NUCs. Others still pertain more to the sphere of dissemination, such as inviting the press to publicise public events, use social media to disseminate the work of the project, or simply using word-of-mouth and personal contacts to reach a wider audience.

Just as in the case of the trade-off between engagement and fatigue, here too there is a proviso to be noted in the realm of recruitment. Two strong limits to recruitment were brought to the fore during informal conversations with LL Coordinators and LL members. The first is related to the (human, financial and time-related) resources needed to manage a greater number of stakeholders, which not all coordinating entities have at all times. The second concerns possible contextual blockages, as, for example, an economic recession at national level that provides disincentives for consumers to buy what are usually more expensive NUCs, all the more as DIVINFOOD gives priority to organic and agroecological farming. Consequently it leads to (some) farmer disengagement in the NUC agroecological value chain. In both cases, this means that recruitment will vary across contexts and has to be carefully paced.

A final note on what the above can suggest in terms of the way forward. In DIVINFOOD formal and informal gatherings, the above reflections have helped LL members learn from each other and have given them ideas as what to put in place in the next years to foster engagement and recruitment. For example, taking the cue from the Portuguese LL, another LL is considering making the work of DIVINFOOD more visible, thereby arousing curiosity, by putting up signs in the LL fields and stickers on the doors of the restaurants it engages with. Another still would like to organize more convivial activities that help reflect on the pathway from farm to fork, such as events where recipes are shared among all stakeholders so as to spark a discussion on what types of seeds were used for that specific dish. Other ideas concern organizing smaller groups for discussions on specific topics or setting up a virtual platform to help the LL members communicate better.

6. References

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7. Appendices

Appendix 1. Questions included in the online monitoring tool

- a) Name of Living Lab and person filling in the tool
- b) Which event/meeting/activity are you reporting on?
- c) Who organized the event/meeting/activity?
- d) Was your event/meeting/activity: online, face-to-face, hybrid?
- e) If it was face-to-face, where did it take place?
- f) What was the objective of the meeting/event/activity? Was it linked to a specific WP/Task? If so, which one?
- g) Do you think that the objectives were fulfilled? If not, why? Any particular challenges you had to face?
- h) Who attended the meeting/event/activity? (number and types of stakeholders)
- i) If someone came for the first time, please briefly describe who, how you "recruited" them and why.
- j) Did you use any particular methods/tools to facilitate participation and engagement? Please briefly describe (e.g. social media, stimulated everyone in the group to talk, etc).
- k) Anything else of relevance you would like to mention?

Appendix 2. Blank template of the Milestone 3 Workplan

DIVINFOOD

DIVINFOOD : Co-constructing interactive short and mid-tier food chains to value agrobiodiversity in healthy plant-based FOOD

Co-constructing interactive short and mid-tier food chains to value agrobiodiversity in healthy plant-based FOOD

Presentation of Living Labs status and plans

LL

presentation

Name (Organization)
(Country)

Living Lab TODAY

Living Lab statement

DIVINFOOD : Co-constructing interactive short and mid-tier food chains to value agrobiodiversity in healthy plant-based FOOD

In LL, we have TODAY

Who is part of your LL	Main role
For example: 1 LL coordinator	-
.....
.....	-

DIVINFOOD : Co-constructing interactive short and mid-tier food chains to value agrobiodiversity in healthy plant-based FOOD

The LL, today

DIVINFOOD : Co-constructing interactive short and mid-tier food chains to value agrobiodiversity in healthy plant-based FOOD

Define your Living Lab

CHARACTERISTIC	DESCRIPTION	EXAMPLE
SENTINEL	CHARACTERISTIC OF A healthy system that is able to detect and respond to changes in its environment.	
SMART AND FLEXIBLE	CHARACTERISTIC OF a healthy system that is able to learn from its environment and adapt to changes.	
ROBUST	CHARACTERISTIC OF a healthy system that is able to withstand and recover from disturbances.	
PERFORMANT	CHARACTERISTIC OF a healthy system that is able to produce the desired outputs.	
ADAPTIVE	CHARACTERISTIC OF a healthy system that is able to change its behavior in response to changes in its environment.	
CONNECTORS AND COLLECTORS	CHARACTERISTIC OF a healthy system that is able to link different parts of the system together.	
SMALL AND OPERATIVE	CHARACTERISTIC OF a healthy system that is able to function at a small scale.	
RELIABLE	CHARACTERISTIC OF a healthy system that is able to provide consistent outputs over time.	
SYSTEMIC	CHARACTERISTIC OF a healthy system that is able to function as a whole, rather than as a collection of parts.	

What animal is your LL at present?
Animals we find our LL familiar with... and why

DIVINFOOD : Co-constructing interactive short and mid-tier food chains to value agrobiodiversity in healthy plant-based FOOD

YOUR LL ASPIRATIONS FOR THE FUTURE

CHARACTERISTIC	DESCRIPTION	EXAMPLE
SENTINEL	CHARACTERISTIC OF A healthy system that is able to detect and respond to changes in its environment.	
SMART AND FLEXIBLE	CHARACTERISTIC OF a healthy system that is able to learn from its environment and adapt to changes.	
ROBUST	CHARACTERISTIC OF a healthy system that is able to withstand and recover from disturbances.	
PERFORMANT	CHARACTERISTIC OF a healthy system that is able to produce the desired outputs.	
ADAPTIVE	CHARACTERISTIC OF a healthy system that is able to change its behavior in response to changes in its environment.	
CONNECTORS AND COLLECTORS	CHARACTERISTIC OF a healthy system that is able to link different parts of the system together.	
SMALL AND OPERATIVE	CHARACTERISTIC OF a healthy system that is able to function at a small scale.	
RELIABLE	CHARACTERISTIC OF a healthy system that is able to provide consistent outputs over time.	
SYSTEMIC	CHARACTERISTIC OF a healthy system that is able to function as a whole, rather than as a collection of parts.	

What animal does your LL aspire to be in 5 years?
Animals we aspire to be in 5 years

LL statement for the future

DIVINFOOD : Co-constructing interactive short and mid-tier food chains to value agrobiodiversity in healthy plant-based FOOD

List 3 main achievements during the 5 Years of the Project

- Achievement 1:
- Achievement 2:
- Achievement 3:

DIVINFOOD : Co-constructing interactive short and mid-tier food chains to value agrobiodiversity in healthy plant-based FOOD

DIVINFOOD : Co-constructing interactive short and mid-tier food chains to value agrobiodiversity in healthy plant-based FOOD

Living Lab

WP	Your LL main role	Your LL main activities	Your role as LL coordinator
WP1			
WP2			
WP3			
WP4			
WP5			
WP6			

Thinking of the achievements you just indicated, please list the expected/desired consequences in the long term (i.e. in 10 years)

TANGIBLE OUTCOMES

INTANGIBLE OUTCOMES

Appendix 3. Blank template of the poster

LL Name
LL coordinator name and contact

Add red circle / dots on the map to show where your LL is located

LL's goals (when the project started)

Main activities
(developed since March 2022)

Current map of actors taking part to the LL

Add here 3-4 photos of activities carried out in the LL for the DIVINFOOD project, put a caption in few key words

Lessons Learned
(In bullets points highlight 2-3 main outcomes both tangible and intangible)

Challenges and strengths
(In bullets points highlight 2-3 main strengths and challenges)

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